

Chemical effects of anodic contact glow discharge electrolysis : Formation of amino acid

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Abstract : In Contact Glow Discharge Electrolysis (CGDE), a plasma is sustained by d.c. glow discharges between an electrode and the electrolyte around it. The chemical results of CGDE are significantly non faradaic. With the anodic plasma in an aqueous electrolyte, non-faradaic results originate mainly from break-up of liquid water molecules near the plasma | anolyte interface by sufficiently energized $\text{H}_2\text{O}_{\text{gas}}^+$ ions coming out of the plasma into H^\bullet and OH^\bullet in yields as high as 13 moles per mol electron of electricity. The radical generating potentiality of anodic CGDE in high local concentration in liquid phase has been explored as a tool for synthesizing amino acids from ammoniacal solution of carboxylates. The results show that amino acids such as glycine from ammoniacal acetate electrolyte and α -alanine from ammoniacal propionate electrolyte are formed in yields exceeding the Faraday law value. The formation of amino acid by anodic CGDE has been explained by radical scavenging action of ammonia and carboxylates on H^\bullet and OH^\bullet radicals and by mutual interaction between $^\bullet\text{NH}_2$ and $\text{RC}^\bullet\text{HCOO}^-$ radicals formed. The present technique requires 0.1-0.2 kcal for production of 10^{-5} mol of glycine as compared to 24 kcal by spark discharge and 50 kcal by X-ray for glycine production from constituents of reducing atmosphere.

Keywords : Contact glow electrolysis, non-faradaic yields, amino acid.

Contact Glow Discharge Electrolysis (CGDE) is an unconventional electrolysis in which a plasma is sustained by d.c. glow discharges between an electrode and the liquid electrolyte around it. It develops spontaneously during normal electrolysis at high voltages. The critical voltage for the onset of CGDE in an aqueous electrolyte is 410 V at the anode and 160 V at the cathode¹⁻³. The chemical effects of CGDE are remarkably non-faradaic, e.g. in anodic CGDE H_2 1.55 mol. mol electron⁻¹, H_2O_2 0.55 mol. mol electron⁻¹ and O_2 0.83 mol. mol electron⁻¹ are produced and in cathodic CGDE O_2 0.46 mol mol electron⁻¹ and H_2 1.37 mol. mol electron⁻¹ are produced with an inert-type aqueous electrolyte such as K_2SO_4 ^{4,5}.

It has been shown^{5,6} that these non-faradaic yields originate in two reaction zones : (i) within the plasma around the glow discharge electrode and (ii) the liquid phase near the plasma | electrolyte interface. Further the percentage yield of non-faradaic product of anodic CGDE is 20-55 from the plasma reaction zone and 45-80 from the liquid phase reaction zone depending on the voltage applied and the contribution of plasma zone is above 25% when the voltage increases beyond 450 V. The products

from the liquid phase reaction zone of anodic CGDE (H_2 , H_2O_2 and O_2^{E} i.e. O_2 in excess of the Faraday's law value) originate through mutual interactions among radicals H^\bullet and OH^\bullet generated there from the break-up of liquid H_2O molecules by bombardment of highly energized $\text{H}_2\text{O}_{\text{gas}}^+$ ions coming out of the anodic plasma^{5,6}.

Obviously anodic CGDE is a potential tool for generating radicals in high local concentration. An estimate of the yield of OH^\bullet radicals produced in the liquid phase reaction zone was made by analysis of the chemical results⁷ of anodic CGDE of cerous sulphate solution and the value was found to be 12-13 mol mol electron⁻¹. Anodic CGDE thus through the use of judiciously chosen radical scavengers as additives to the electrolyte, can be explored as a tool for synthesis of compounds. Infact anodic CGDE has been shown to produce oxalic acid from formic acids⁸ and polyacrylamide from acrylamide⁹.

In an extension of these studies, the possibility of exploring anodic CGDE as a tool for synthesizing amino acids based on scavenging potential of ammonia and carboxylates for H^\bullet and OH^\bullet was examined. The results obtained with ammoniacal acetates and propionates on

the formation of glycine and α -alanine are described and discussed here.

Results and discussion

The results obtained on the formation of glycine and α -alanine by anodic CGDE of ammoniacal carboxylate solutions under varying quantities of electricity and anolyte composition are presented in Tables 1, 2 and 3.

As seen from Table 1, the yield of glycine increases with quantities of electricity passed, however, the rate of increase in the yield decreases with increase in the quantity of electricity passed and the yield finally attains a stationary value above 18 C.

$$(\text{glycine}) = \left(1 - e^{-G_0 q \frac{k}{V}} \right) \frac{V}{k} \quad (2)$$

where V is the volume of anolyte and q is the quantity of electricity (mol electron).

Further as seen from Table 1, the yield at any quantity of electricity exceeds significantly the value stipulated by Faraday's laws. The yield in considerable excess of Faraday law value is observed for formation of glycine and α -alanine also, during anodic CGDE in electrolytes of different composition as described in Tables 1, 2 and 3.

Table 1. Effect of quantities of electricity on the yield of glycine (anolyte, 0.25 M CH₃COONH₄ plus 1.70 M NH₄OH (fixed composition); catholyte, 0.005 M K₂SO₄; voltage applied, 480 V; current passed, 35 ± 5 mA)

Sl. no.	Quantity of electricity (C)	Yield of glycine (10 ⁻⁴ mol) ± 0.5 × 10 ⁻⁴	Yield corresponding to Faraday's law (10 ⁻⁴ mol)
1.	5.03	6.17	0.52
2.	10.01	9.60	1.03
3.	15.02	13.71	1.56
4.	18.01	15.77	1.87
5.	20.02	15.60	2.07
6.	30.01	17.14	3.10
7.	40.01	16.18	4.15

The yield vs quantity of electricity (mol electron) plot (Fig. 1) shows that glycine forms initially at a rate proportional to the current passed. However, when the concentration of glycine builds up, it starts decomposing. Assuming that the rate of decomposition of glycine is dependent on the current as well as its concentration, the expression for the net rate of formation of glycine will be,

$$\frac{d(\text{glycine})}{dt} = G_0 \frac{I}{F} - G_0 \frac{I}{F} k[\text{glycine}] \quad (1)$$

where (glycine) is its integral yield (mol), G_0 is the initial differential yield (mol. mol electron⁻¹) measured as the slope of the linear part of the yield vs mol electron curve (Fig. 1) at the origin, I is the current, k is the rate constant of decomposition of glycine and F is Faraday constant.

On integrating the eq. (1) and applying the condition that there is no glycine at the start of electrolysis, the equation becomes,

Results of the effect of anolyte composition on the yield of amino acid show an interesting trend (Tables 2 and 3). Whereas with increase in concentration of each of the components of the anolyte (NH₄OH, RCH₂COO⁻ and NH₄⁺), the amino acid yield shows an upward trend, NH₄⁺ as compared to the other two components has a much more pronounced effect. Further, in absence of added NH₄⁺ ion, no significant yield of amino acid could be detected (Tables 2 and 3). The presence of NH₄⁺ at significant concentrations in the anolyte causes enhancing the concentration of undissociated ammonia to an extent for its effective kinetic competition with H[•] and OH[•] for scavenging of H[•] and OH[•] leading to amino acid formation (rate constants for reactions of H[•] or OH[•] with amino or carboxylate scavengers are at least two order of magnitude less than with H[•] or OH[•] themselves¹² – further is discussed below). It seems that NH₄⁺ ion from the added ammonium salts has no other role on the formation of amino acid. NH₄⁺ is unreactive to H[•] and OH[•]¹². Infact the non-faradaic yield of H₂ in anodic CGDE of (NH₄)₂SO₄ solutions which originates through mutual interactions of H[•], is very similar to that of K₂SO₄ solutions : yield of

Fig. 1. Variation of the yield of glycine with quantity of electricity (q) during anodic CGDE of ammonium acetate solution at 480 V

Table 2. Chemical effects of anodic CGDE of ammoniacal acetate solutions : Formation of glycine - Effect of anolyte composition

Sl. no.	Anolyte composition (M)				Yield of glycine (10^{-4} mol) $\pm 0.5 \times 10^{-4}$	Yield corresponding to Faraday's laws (10^{-4} mol)
	NH_4OH	$\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4$	CH_3COOK	$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$		
^a Set 1 : anolyte, $\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4$ plus NH_4OH (variable composition); catholyte, $0.005 M \text{K}_2\text{SO}_4$ (fixed composition); voltage applied, 480-500 V d.c.; current passed, 37.5 ± 2.5 mA; coulombs passed, 30 C.						
1.	1.80	0.10	-	-	4.26	3.10
2.	1.80	0.15	-	-	8.88	3.10
3.	1.80	0.20	-	-	11.90	3.10
4.	1.80	0.30	-	-	22.08	3.10
5.	1.80	0.40	-	-	28.08	3.10
6.	0.85	0.25	-	-	16.49	3.10
7.	1.80	0.25	-	-	16.62	3.10
8.	2.75	0.25	-	-	18.24	3.10
^b Set 2 : anolyte, mixture of CH_3COOK and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ (variable composition) plus NH_4OH (fixed composition); catholyte, $0.05 M \text{K}_2\text{SO}_4$ (fixed composition); voltage applied, 410 V d.c.; current passed, 45 ± 5 mA; coulombs passed, 30 C.						
9.	1.70	-	0.25	-	Nil	-
10.	1.70	-	0.25	0.12	19.20	3.10
11.	1.70	-	0.12	0.12	19.32	3.10
12.	1.70	-	0.06	0.12	17.28	3.10
13.	1.70	-	0.12	0.09	12.18	3.10
14.	1.70	-	0.12	0.06	7.73	3.10
15.	1.70	-	0.18	0.09	12.66	3.10
16.	1.70	-	0.25	0.06	7.74	3.10

^a K_2SO_4 (catholyte concentration was higher in Set 2 than in Set 1 for maintenance of steady CGDE as the anolyte composition differ in the two sets and accordingly voltage necessary was lower in Set 2 than in Set 1 due to higher IR drop in Set 1).

Table 3. Chemical effects of anodic CGDE of ammoniacal propionate solutions : Formation of alanine – Effect of anolyte composition (anolyte, C₂H₅COONa, (NH₄)₂SO₄ plus NH₄OH (variable composition); catholyte, 0.02 M K₂SO₄ (fixed composition); voltage applied, 410 V d.c.; current passed 40 ± 5 mA; quantity of electricity, 30 C.

Sl. no.	Anolyte composition (M)			Yield of α-alanine (10 ⁻⁴ mol) ± 0.5 × 10 ⁻⁴	Yield corresponding to Faraday's law (10 ⁻⁴ mol)
	C ₂ H ₅ COONa	(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	NH ₄ OH		
1.	0.25	0.00	1.60	-	-
2.	0.25	0.12	1.60	21.44	3.10
3.	0.12	0.12	1.60	20.54	3.10
4.	0.06	0.12	1.60	20.80	3.10
5.	0.25	0.06	1.60	8.47	3.10
6.	0.25	0.03	1.60	3.73	3.10
7.	0.25	0.12	0.80	20.32	3.10
8.	0.25	0.12	3.30	21.12	3.10

H₂ is 1.78 mol. mol electron⁻¹ in K₂SO₄ and 1.72 mol. mol electron⁻¹ in (NH₄)₂SO₄.

The formation of amino acid can thus be explained by the scavenging action of both NH₃ and RCH₂COO⁻ on H[•] and OH[•] radicals. These radicals are generated during anodic CGDE near the plasma | anolyte interface by the break-up of liquid water molecules there by bombardment of H₂O_{gas}⁺ ions which get highly energized while coming out of the plasma into the anolyte^{1,5,6,11}. It may be noted that cathode fall for anodic CDGE, which is located at the plasma|anolyte interface was measured¹ to be 410 V. The reactions occurring near the plasma | anolyte interface are thus :

The formation of H[•] and OH[•] during CGDE was confirmed by an ESR study using DMPO as the spin trap¹¹. The H[•] and OH[•] radicals would mutually interact to produce H₂, O₂ and H₂O₂^{1,5,6}.

In the presence of NH₃ and carboxylate anion which would scavenge H[•] and OH[•] the following mechanism is envisaged for formation of amino acids.

Mutual interactions between the radicals thus formed would lead to formation of amino acids :

In course of anodic CGDE the concentration of amino acid keeps increasing and when the concentration of an amino acid becomes sufficient, the amino acid is attacked by OH[•] and H[•] also

NH₂CH[•]COOH would undergo further breakdown by oxidation with OH[•]. Radical induced degradation of amino acid has been studied by radiolysis¹² and by a form of glow discharge electrolysis in which the electrode was just in contact with the solution but not immersed in the electrolyte¹³. This reaction (12) accounts for the attainment of a stationary yield for glycine during increases in the quantity of electricity. The present method requires 0.01–0.02 kcal for production of 10⁻⁵ mol of glycine as compared to 24 kcal by spark discharge technique and 50 kcal by X-ray for glycine production from constituents of reducing atmospheres¹⁴. Further production of glycine from acetonitrile or methyl amine was reported¹⁵ by a glow discharge electrolysis technique where the anode was not immersed in the electrolyte (incorrectly described

as CGDE) with an efficiency 2–4 kcal for 10^{-5} mol of glycine. Thus the present technique is more potential and efficient for production of amino acids as compared to other discharge or radiation methods.

Experimental

A H-type cell fitted with 5 mm long platinum-wire anode (dia 0.35 mm), 1 cm^2 platinum-foil cathode (thickness 0.20 mm), gas exit tubes, mercury-in-glass thermometer and a G-5 glass sinter as electrode compartment separator was used as the cell for investigating the synthesis of amino acids by anodic CGDE. Both the electrodes were immersed in the electrolyte to a depth of atleast 2 cm. The anolyte used was an ammoniacal mixture of ammonium and carboxylate salts at varying concentrations of the components of the anolyte and the catholyte was $0.005\text{--}0.05 \text{ M K}_2\text{SO}_4$. Power was supplied from an Aplab 7323 d.c. regulated power supply ($V = 50\text{--}1000 \text{ V}$ and $I_{\text{max}} = 1 \text{ A}$) and current was measured by a multirange (0–500 mA) milliammeter (OSAW). Voltage was measured by multirange (0–600 V) voltmeter (Alcock) and the quantity of electricity by an ESC 640 Digital Coulometer. Pressure was atmospheric and the ambient temperature was $20 \pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The applied voltage was 410–500 V and quantities of electricity passed was 5–40 C. The electrolysed solution from the anode chamber showed positive Ninhydrin test for amino acid. It was shown by one and two-dimensional paper chromatography that the amino acid formed from ammoniacal acetate anolyte was glycine only and that from ammoniacal propionate anolyte was α -alanine only. The amino acid formed in each case under varying anolyte composition and quantities of electricity was quantitatively determined by spectrophotometry of copper chelate of alanine at 620 nm following the standard procedure of "Copper Salt method of Amino acids and Peptides", developed by Spies and Chambers¹⁰.

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade.

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